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Research Article

COMPARISON OF THE GLYCEMIC CONTROL AND FETO-MATERNAL OUTCOMES IN THE PATIENTS OF GESTATIONAL DIABETES TREATED BY INSULIN VERSUS METFORMIN**Dr Prof Muhammad Ali, Dr Warda Khan, Dr Saima Shams**
DHQ Teaching Hospital Dera Ghazi Khan**Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of this research work is to compare and assess the glyceemic control and feto-maternal results in the patients of gestational diabetes treated insulin and metformin.

Methodology: The duration of this research work was from 2016 to 2018 in DHQ Teaching Hospital Dera Ghazi Khan. Total seventy-one person suffering from gestational diabetes mellitus who were included in this research work. We obtained the consent from all the patients. We separated the patients into 2 groups. On the group-A, thirty-two females obtained the oral metformin 500.0 milligram TDS whereas thirty-nine female patients of Group-B obtained insulin 0.80-0.90 mg/kg per day in 2 separated doses intravenously. We followed the patients till term. We evaluated the feto-maternal results in twenty-five patients in every group who remained in this research till end.

Results: When we compared both groups, new births from the females of Group-B were present with more weight. An important proportion of babies were delivered after thirty-eight pregnancy weeks from the females of Group-B. Total 2 intra-uterine deaths occurred and there was much high HbA1C level at term in the females of Group-B. There was not significant FBS at complete term and there was high occurrence of the CS (Cesarean Section) because of the feto-maternal imbalance in the females of Group-B (28.0% vs .20%). We also analyzed the results for the glyceemic control pre and post treatment showed that there was statistically less FBS in the females of Group-A, while in the females of Group-B, the level of HbA1C and FBS.

Conclusion: There were better impacts of metformin on the feto-maternal results and glyceemic control as compared to the insulin in the patients of gestational diabetes mellitus.

KEYWORDS: Gestation, Delivery, Cesarean Section, Intra-Uterine, Pregnancy, Insulin, Metformin.

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INTRODUCTION:

Intolerance to the level of glucose happening in the duration of prenatal period, identification of the gestational diabetes mellitus is possible in the 2nd pregnancy trimester. The main reasons of the dysfunctions causing the deficiency of insulin in gestational diabetes mellitus are fully explainable. Some of the most important reasons are auto-immune dysfunction of the beta cell, reduced secretion of insulin, insulin resistance and adiposity in the period of pregnancy. A data of fifteen years from 1995 to 2010 showed that the prevalence of the gestational diabetes mellitus in the whole world ranges from 3 to 4.40%. The most common prevalence recorded in the females of South Asia with a rate from 3.20% to 3.50%. There is 72.0% high occurrence of gestational diabetes mellitus in the females with greater than thirty years of age, 50.0 occurs in females with past family history of the disease and 29.0% occur in the females with high BMI. Conventionally, insulin therapy is effectual for the treatment of this complication as it displays appropriate control of increased level of blood glucose. From past many decades, it is in regular use for the treatment of gestational diabetes mellitus during pregnancy.

This has association with the high morbidities as well as mortalities of females like surgical deliveries, maternal hypoglycemia, and high weight gain in the period of pregnancy. Metformin is a medicine which is in regular use for the treatment of the patients suffering from Type-2 DM (Diabetes Mellitus) since 1960. It has got upgradation to the Category-B medicine because it has no association with any fetal congenital abnormalities. It has minimum side effects, so it can be a best alternative for the treatment of the gestational diabetes mellitus in pregnant females. The purpose of this research work was to assess and compare the impacts of insulin and metformin on the fetomaternal outcomes as well as control of the glucose level in the patients of gestational diabetes mellitus.

METHODOLOGY:

This research work carried out in DHQ Teaching Hospital Dera Ghazi Khan from 2016 to 2018. We

obtained the consent of the participant who were high risk patients. The high risk patients were present with past history of the gestational diabetes, intra-uterine deaths, obesity and strong history of disease in the family. seventy-one females with confirm gestational diabetes mellitus in their 2nd trimester of pregnancy were the part of this research work. We separated the patients randomly in 2 groups. We gave Metformin, 500 milligrams to the patients of Group-A three times in a day, with the prescription of dose escalation treatment in one time a day in the early morning and after some time, we increased it to the 3 times in a day according to the requirement. We gave the subcutaneous insulin to the patients of Group-B. The dose of the Insulin was 0.80 units/kg per day in the 2nd trimester and 0.90 units/kg per day in the 3rd trimester. We advised the patients for strict control of their diet. We advised the patients for at least thirty-minute walk three times in a day.

We followed all the patients till their term. We evaluated the fetomaternal outcomes with the delivery mode and fetal outcome just after delivery. SPSS V.17 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information. Chi-square method was in use for the comparison of the variables of both groups.

RESULTS:

We compiled the results of fifty patients who were remained part of our research work with twenty-five patients in each work. When we evaluated the maternal traits, we found no disparity between weight and age of patients present in Group-A and Group-B. We found the statistical disparities between FBS (Fasting Blood Sugar) and level of RBS (Random Blood Sugar) between the patients of both groups. When we compared HbA1C level, we found no significance (Table-1). The babies of the Group-B were more weight as compared to the babies of Group-A. There was no significance in the Apgar score in the patients of both groups. We found the statistically significant results when compared the age at delivery time. All the neonates were healthy in from the females of Group-A while there was 2 intra-uterine deaths in the females of Group-B.

Table-I: Baseline Maternal Characteristics Group-A v/s Group-B (n=50).

Characteristics	Group-A		Group-B		p value
	Mean/No	SD/Percent	Mean/No	SD/Percent	
Age (years)	29.76	3.41	31.60	4.27	0.0990
Weight(kg)	77.90	7.65	77.90	9.03	NA
FBS-1(mg/dl)	104.40	13.12	117.90	29.06	0.0390*
RBS(mg/dl)	171.16	37.44	239.16	69.78	<0.0010*
HbA _{1C} --1 (%)	5.28	0.42	5.43	0.34	0.1820

There was not significant FBS in the patients of both groups. There was high amount of cesarean sections in the females of Group-B because of the feto-maternal disproportion because there were bigger babies (28.0% vs.2.0%) (Table-2).

Table-II: Fetal and Maternal outcomes Group A v/s B (n=50)

Parameters	Fetal outcomes	Group-A		Group-B		P- value
		Mean/No	SD/Percent	Mean/No	SD/Percent	
Weight and Apgar	Weight of the baby (kg)	3.14	0.32	3.44	0.46	0.01*
	Apgar score	8.64	0.56	8.22	2.43	0.39
Delivery age	37 weeks	19.00	76.00	11.00	44.00	0.0210*
	38 weeks	6.00	24.00	14.00	56.00	
Condition of baby	Alive baby	25.00	100.00	23.00	96.00	0.490**
	Intrauterine death	0.00	0.00	2.00	8.00	
	Still birth	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Maternal outcomes	HbA _{1C} -2 (%)	5.42	0.34	5.72	0.35	0.003*
	FBS -2 (36	93.48	11.90	102.08	20.63	0.079
Mode of delivery	Normal vaginal	7.00	28.00	5.00	20.00	N/A
	Assisted delivery	2.00	8.00	3.00	12.00	
	Cesarean section	16.00	64.00	17.00	68.00	
	Cesarean due to bad obstetric history	14.00	56.00	10.00	40.00	
	Cesarean due to feto-maternal disproportion	2.00	8.00	7.00	28.00	

* Statistically Significant

** Fischer Exact Test

When we analyzed the results for the glycemic control pre and post treatment in both groups, we observed that there was less FBS statistically in the females treated with Metformin. There were no significant values of HbA_{1C} in both groups (Table-3).

Table III: HbA1C and FBS at Enrollment And At Term Of Pregnancy

Groups	At enrollment		At term		P- Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Group-A FBS	104.4	13.12	93.43	11.93	0.000*
Group-A HbA1C	5.284	0.42	5.42	0.346	0.0610
Group-B FBS	117.92	29.06	102.08	20.64	0.0020*
Group-B HbA1C	5.43	0.345	5.68	0.506	0.040*

DISCUSSION:

There is increasing prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus in the whole world. There is also high risk for the development of this complication in our population due to the genetic and development factors. There are very serious and long term impacts of this disease on both baby and mother. In time diagnosis and administration of this complication can improve the outcome of this disease. The original values of age, weight levels of HbA1C were without any difference in both groups but patients of both groups were present with the various levels of FBS and RBS. Balani took the same groups for his research work. In his research work, Niromanesh discovered that there were babies from the mothers given insulin as compared to the females treated with metformin. A current research work by Marques announced that there was no disparity in outcome of fetal from the females treated with metformin and insulin. This research work was conducted on a very large size of sample.

We found no disparity in Apgar score between the patients in our research work. Similar results were recorded by Rowan in his comparison of patients with the same groups. Kelley in his research work stated that there was very low maternal gain of weight and low gestational age at the time of delivery treated with metformin in comparison with the insulin treatment. Whereas Territi proposed in his research work that he found no disparity in the patients of both groups when he tabulated the delivery at the gestational age. Hellmuth reported the high rate of intra-uterine mortalities which was much opposite to this current research work.

The most important reason behind this high rate was that most of the females started treatment in their last three months' of pregnancy period. Carson observed in his research work that the infusions of insulin for many days to fetal lamb create a progressive decline in the arterial oxygen content of the fetal and it can be the reason of the high IUDs with insulin therapy. Metformin treatment fulfilled the requirements and demands of the study. Results of the research work conducted by Riazare are in agreement with the

findings of this current research work. Goh in his research work stated that rate of CS was 45.60% in the insulin group which was much high as compared to the metformin group. Kale observed that patients with the insulin treatment for gestational diabetes mellitus were present with high rate of CS. Moore also confirmed in his study that metformin is very effectual substitute of insulin with positive results.

CONCLUSION:

There were better effects of Metformin on the glycemic control and feto-maternal outcomes in the patients of gestational diabetes mellitus as compared to the insulin. So, metformin is a better option as compared to insulin for the patients suffering from gestational diabetes mellitus. There is a need of more research works with huge sample size and in multi-centers for the consolidation of the findings of this research work.

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